

Radioprotection by chemical means with the help of combined regimen radio-protectors – A short review[†]

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Abstract : Radioprotection against ionizing radiation is mostly provided by Chemical Radio-protectors which contain simple chemical molecules. Chemical radioprotection is primarily due to molecules which contain one or more functional groups namely -NH₂, -SH, -COOH, =NH, SPO₃H₂, -OH[•], -H[•] etc. Combined regimen radio-protectors namely 5HTP + AET, 5HTP + cysteamine, 5HTP + MPG, WR 2721 + MPG and Glucan + WR 2721 are specially mentioned.

Combined regimen radio-protectors are used in place of single radio-protector for increased protective efficacy with reduced toxicity (both chemical and radiochemical). Reasons for their use are : (a) restoration in electrolyte balance, (b) capability of Radical Scavenging, (c) these act as an antioxidant, (d) offer defense against peroxidation (viz. poly-unsaturated fatty acids) by enzymes, (e) they act synergistically-primarily for, (f) radical scavenging and (g) regeneration of immune system etc.

Lastly, an effective combined regimen radio-protector has been postulated. The constituents are MnCl₂, ZnCl₂, Solution II, amino-acid mixture, Vitamin C : Vitamin E (18 : 1) when incorporated in a temporal sequence showed excellent radio-protective efficacy (90% survival and 68% CFU counts) and minimum toxicity against lethal dose (i.e. 10 Gy) at a dose rate of about 0.006 Gy/s. A particular protocol was followed for radioprotection here.

Keywords : Introduction, criteria, mode of action for radio-protectors, factors influencing radioprotection, DRF (Dose Reduction Factor), Mode of action, factors influencing radioprotection, radio-protectors in combination : 5HTP + AET; 5HTP + MPG; 5HTP + cysteamine; WR 2721 + MPG; Glucan + WR 2721, postulated combined regimen radio-protectors, percentage survival, CFU counts, toxicity, therapeutic potential, conclusion.

Introduction

Radioprotection is offered by physical, chemical, biochemical, biopolymeric, biological and medicinal compounds either in single or in combination¹. When these compounds are incorporated about 30 min prior to irradiation by gamma-ray, from ⁶⁰Co or ¹³⁷CS radiation source to (Swiss Albino Mice or Rodents) in the dose rate range of 0.067 to 0.335 Gy/s² up to 10 Gy for lethal dose or 4 Gy for sub-lethal dose these species are radio-protected by various mechanisms. Functional abilities for combined regimen radio-protectors and reasons for their use have already been mentioned (Summary section).

Criteria

- (1) It should offer good protection against both acute and chronic radiation dose.
- (2) It should be suitable for oral administration and can be rapidly absorbed and distributed throughout the body (normally intra-peritoneal route of administration is followed for mice).
- (3) It should not show significant toxicity.
- (4) Shelf life should be long, easy handling and storage should be achieved.
- (5) It should be available and inexpensive.

[†]Dedicated to INMAS for advancement of knowledge in Radioprotection.

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Mode of action of radio-protectors

Deleterious effects of radiation occurs in temporal sequence across various levels of organization starting from primary lesion in biomolecules and structures eliciting repair processes, leading to cell death or transformation responsible for morbidity, genetic disorder and cancer¹.

So, various strategies have been developed to protect biological systems by interfering with the development of radiation damage. Physico-chemical and radio-biological properties of some well-known chemical radio-protectors has been reported by us¹.

Factors influencing radioprotection

Radioprotection depends upon structure of the molecule, its molecular weight, dose or concentration of radio-protector to be incorporated, biological species in which incorporation has been done, dose reduction factor (DRF) or dose modifying factor (DMF), type and quality of radiation, dose rate and total dose, pre-exposure time, availability of radio-protectors, time interval between radio-protector administration and maximum protection etc.¹⁻³. For most radio-protectors maximum protection is achieved when administered between 15 to 60 min before irradiation. Radioprotection studies are done by *vitro*^{4,5} and *in vivo* methods^{6,7} with cell population using micro-colony assay, animal percentage survival⁷ and by endogenous spleen counts⁸. (Kindly consult Table 1 given in a separate page with this manuscript which should be incorporated here).

Dose reduction factor (DRF) or dose modifying factor (DMF)²

It is defined by an equation given below :

DRF (Dose Reduction Factor) =

$$\frac{LD_{50}(30) \text{ for radioprotected group of animals}}{LD_{50}(30) \text{ for unirradiated group of animals}} \quad (1)$$

where $LD_{50}(30)$ = Lethal dose (~ 10 Gy) at which 50 per cent of the animals die for an observation period of 30 days².

Radioprotectors in combination

The basic reason for combination is to obtain reduced toxicity, a greater protective efficacy and greater thera-

peutic potential as these are not obtainable by a single radio-protector. Ionizing radiation causes derangement of the functions of : (1) electrolyte balance, (2) cellular and nucleolar membranes and (3) DNA repair enzymes etc. It is not possible to achieve it by a single radio-protector.

A combined regimen should be capable of radical scavenging, acting as an anti-oxidant, offering defense against peroxidation of poly-unsaturated fatty acids in membrane phospholipids etc. it should be able to supplement co-factors responsible for functioning of enzymes that contain Mn and Zn as trace elements, maintenance of electrolyte balance, necessary energy supply and maintenance of levels of plasma amino-acids etc. Some physico-chemical parameters like membrane permeability with cellular and nucleolar membranes, diffusion co-efficient of the components, interaction possibilities with body fluids, bio-distribution etc. should be known.

5HTP + AET

For about 30 years, this combination in a ratio of 5 : 1 by weight = 90.82 : 14.23 micro-molar ratio has been reported to give radioprotection to different biological systems in the dose range of 4 to 12 Gy/s for Cobalt-60 gamma rays^{7,20}. While AET is toxic, 5HTP is not. The combination of 5HTP + AET has been proved to be much better for radio-protective purposes than 5HTP alone against a gamma ray dose of 10.5 Gy and 12.5 Gy without any significant toxicity to any other tissues or organs, except kidney and testis. A complex is formed between 5HTP and AET and radiation-induced changes in the complex have been noted²¹. Routine haematological examination and biochemical estimation of blood and urine have yielded normal values. Reversal studies done after 30 days of stopping the drug administration to animals, kidney histological damage disappeared and in all the animals testis damage was completely cured. 5HTP + AET was encapsulated in RBC membrane ghost and it was found to provide radioprotection against lethal dose at about 1/200th amount needed for radioprotection compared to free 5HTP + AET^{22,23}.

Thiols in combination

5HTP + MPG combination protects the whole body of mice up to a dose of 10.5 Gy, but not up to 12.5 Gy²⁴.

Table 1. Physico-chemical and radiobiological properties of some well-known chemical radio-protectors

Radio-protector	Structure	Molecular weight	Dose	Biological material	DRF	Effect	Type of radiation and dose rate	Ref. No.
Cysteine	$\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-SH}$ COOH	121.20	40 mg/day	Male mice	1.19	Survival	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 0.35 Gy/s	9
Cystamine	$\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-S}$ $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-S}$	153.33	50 mg/kg	Wister rats	1.79	Survival	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 0.063 Gy/s	10
Cystamine	$\text{SH-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-NH}_2$ $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-S}$	77.20	150 mg/kg	Rat cerebral cortex	1.30	Degeneration	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 0.05 Gy/s	11
5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5-HTP)	 $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH-COOH}$ NH_2	220.20	200 mg/kg	Male mice	1.20	Survival	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 10.5 Gy	12
5-Hydroxytryptamine (5-HT)	 $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$ NH_2	175.20	3 mg/0.5 ml	Female mice	-	Survival	X-Ray; 6.75 Gy	13
β -Mercaptopyruvyl-glycine (MPG)	$\text{CH}_3\text{-CH-CONH-CH}_2\text{-COOH}$ SH	163.20	20 mg/kg	Male mice	-	Survival	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 15 Gy	14, 15
β -Aminoethyl-isothiouoniumbromide hydro-bromide (AET)	$\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-S-C=NH}$ NH_2	281.04	0.45 mM/kg	Mouse cells	1.20 to 1.34	Reduced frequency of polychromatic erythrocytes	$^{60}\text{Co-}\gamma$; 0.24 Gy/s	16
Glutathione	CONH $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH-(CH}_2\text{)}_2\text{-CONH-CH}$ COOH CH_2SH	307.33	-	Ehrlich ascites tumor cell lines	-	Average DNA content per cell	X-Ray; 20 Gy	17
WR 2721	$\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-NH}$ CH_2OH $\text{SPO}_3\text{H}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$	232.25	400 mg/kg	Male mice	1.75	Survival	$^{137}\text{Cs-}\gamma$; 0.0195 Gy/s	18

5HTP + Cysteamine provide protection against 10.5 Gy. Most of the active sulphur containing radio-protective chemicals (viz. MPG, MEA, WR 2721) are toxic to living systems. These combined regimens decrease DNA synthesis and prolong the cell cycle of stem cells in small intestine. But in protective dose nucleus, mitochondria and endoplasmic reticulum get structurally deformed²⁵.

WR 2721 + MPG combination in the ratio of (50 mg/kg) + (20 mg/kg) protects bone marrow cells against radiation dose as determined by chromosomal aberration studies. With increase in dose of drug administered, protection is increased. Administration of MPG after WR 2721 helps to maintain the higher GSH level compared to WR 2721 alone²⁶. By combining these two drugs it is possible to minimize toxic effect and increase protective effect²⁴.

Glucan + WR 2721 have a DRF of 1.5 to 1.6 whereas only Glucan has a DRF of 1.2 to 1.3. Glucan is a potential therapeutic agent as it stimulates immune system. It also reduces the behavioral toxicity of WR 2721²⁷.

Postulated combined regimen radio-protector (Ready for phase I and phase II clinical trial) :

Constituents of this combined regimen are :

(1) Solution II (i.e. 145 mM; NaCl, 5mM; KCl, 4 mM; MgCl₂, 7.6 mM; Na₂HPO₄, 2.4 mM; NaH₂PO₄, 10 mM glucose).

(2) Amino-acid mixture (200 micromolar) each of L-cysteine, L-leucine, 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan and L-tyrosine.

(3) MnCl₂ (180 micromolar in isotonic solution) and ZnCl₂ (37 micromolar/kg).

(4) Vitamin C : Vitamin E = 18.1 concentration ratio.

This has been postulated by us. Protocol for incorporation of these constituents into Swiss Albino mice is Streptomycin treatment (35 mg/ml) – 5 days ahead of any other treatment. 0.5 ml (35 mg/ml), MnCl₂ in isotonic solution (180 micromolar/kg body weight) – 3 days before irradiation was followed by 0.5 ml ZnCl₂ (37 micromolar/kg body weight) – 1 day before irradiation and solution II = 0.5 ml. Amino-acid mixture (200 micromolar each) of cysteine, 5HTP, tyrosine and leucine = 0.5

ml. Vitamin C (25 mg/ml) – 0.5 ml : Vitamin E (1.38 mg/g of oil) = 0.5 ml were administered intra-peritoneally on the same day as the gamma irradiation of mice were performed. Vitamin E was incorporated 30 min after Vitamin C¹⁹. Each constituent was incorporated keeping a gap of 30 min in between 30 min time was given after incorporation of all constituents. Gamma irradiation was done in a Gamma cell (dose rate was 0.006 Gy/s). This dose rate was determined by FBX dosimetry²⁸.

The observation period was 30 days in all these experiments. Number of mice in all sets of experiments was 5. But the full combined regimen radio-protector incorporated group of mice (total number of mice were 16) were irradiated to 10 Gy. Control group, 2.5 Gy group, 4.0 Gy group, 7.5 Gy group and 10 Gy group – each group contained 5 mice. In one set no radio-protector was used while in a second set Vitamin C : Vitamin E (18 : 1 concentration ratio) and in the third set all the constituents were administered intra-peritoneally. Both percentage survival studies and spleen colony formation studies have proved the combined regimen radio-protector excellent¹⁹, the respective values of percentage survival and spleen colony formation values being 90% and 68%.

Conclusion

Combined regimen radio-protectors are non-toxic, more effective and have therapeutic potential. The postulated one should undergo phase I and II clinical trials. It is expected that it will bring relief to the radiation-induced cancer patients.

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Abbreviations

Gy – Gray, Gy/s – Gray/s, 5HTP – 5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan, AET – β -Aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide, MPG – β -Mercaptopropionyl glycine, WR 2721 – Amifostine, Glucan – Biological radio-protector, CFU – Colony formation unit (colonies are formed in spleen), GSH – Glutathione, DNA – Deoxyribonucleic acid, DRF – Dose reduction factor, $MnCl_2$ – Manganese chloride, $ZnCl_2$ – Zinc chloride and Solution II – A mixture of electrolytes (mentioned in the text).

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